

Library Use as Correlate in Curbing the Spread of Fake News on Social Media Among Private University Students in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Fake news is seen as stories that contain misleading and fake facts which aim at either spreading propaganda or influencing the audience's views. Alternatively, fake news refers to news messages that contain incorrect or false information. Fake news can be made available in print or non-print but the fastest means through which fake news travel farer is the social media. The spread of fake news on social media becomes more concern as private university students especially the ones from average social status families who could easily afford and access smart phones, internet, computer, and power now sleeps on online. The study adopted descriptive survey design method. Random sampling technique method was used to select respondents from six (6) private universities in Oyo state Nigeria. Data were collected through questionnaire. Data collected were analysed based on frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that the most prevalent fake news in private universities are those related to celebrities and entertainment, social issues and activism, and political news. It was also discovered that library resources were valuable in evaluating news on social media, as well as most students use library resources to fact-check information on social media. The study therefore recommended that private university libraries should expand their role as a hub for fact-checking by offering workshops and providing access to tools that help students verify the authenticity of information.

Keywords: Fake news, library use, social media and private university

Introduction

Fake news has been one of the most discussed topics in the contemporary society both public and scientific since the 2016 U.S. presidential campaign (Nelson & Taneja, 2018). Fake news was originally applied to political satire, it now seems to stand for all things 'inaccurate' (Tambini, 2017) and is even applied in contexts that are completely unrelated to mediated communication (Packer, 2017). Researchers have

not been able to provide a definite definition of the term. However, several authors have given different definition of the term from different perspective.

The term 'fake news' stands for something larger than the term itself, it is the expression of a larger and fundamental shift within the technological and political underpinnings of mediated communication in modern democracies. Contemporary discourses, particularly media

coverage, defined fake news as viral posts based on fake accounts made to look like real news reports. Allcott and Gentzkow (2017) admit that fake news is intentionally and verifiably false that is capable of misleading readers. Fake news has become a buzzword, especially after the 2016 presidential elections in the United States, a democratic exercise marked by loads of misinformation and false news. The flow of misinformation around the 2016 United State presidential election put the problem of fake news on the agenda all over the world. Wardle (2017) sees fake news as fabricated news reports produced either for profit or for political purposes. Leonhardt and Thompson (2017) describe fake news as a type of propaganda or yellow and misleading journalism that consists of deliberate misinformation, spread via traditional media (print or non-print) that is, online social media. In their contributions, Tandoc, Lim, and Ling (2018) elaborates more by providing an overview of the various types of fake news, which includes; news satire, news parody, fabrication, manipulation, advertising and propaganda. Fake news therefore could be seen as stories that contain misleading and fake facts which aim at either spreading propaganda or influencing the audience's political views, or at producing a funny content and making a profit. In other words, fake news refers to news messages that contain incorrect or false information but do not report the incorrectness or false of information. Fake news can be made available in print or non-print but the fastest means through which fake news travel farer in couple of minutes include social media (non-print).

The Internet has significantly changed the type of news that consumers receive. In the past consumers relied on traditional media, such as newspaper, radio and television which involved relatively fewer and more established sources of news. Nowadays consumers are exposed to online sources of information, through social networking sites, which allow any individual to share content without fact-checking or editorial judgment (Allcott and Gentzkow, 2017). Many worried that social media sources may publish fake or false information and present it as facts or real news. Easy access to social media platforms has created a tsunami of news and information flows to eager and unwitting audiences and markets alike around the world, with significant implications on users' consumption patterns and attitudes toward the topics shared. For better or worse social media has become a major driver on determining political

outcomes, including in politically fragile nations, emerging communities, and industrialized regions. In recent times, social media platforms have become the new vox populi pushing away dictatorial regimes and fostering misinformation, fake news and related forms of free speech. Studies show social media use both as a post-truth engine and a hate-monger. In 2016 United State Presidential Election for example, fake news articles published on social media and widely distributed by mainstream media about the candidates' social life ushers in social media as an essential source of news. That style of communication suggests the democratic process itself is under threat. The study of Alcott and Gentzkow (2017) have found that fake news stories appearing social media platforms three months before the election, those favoring then Presidential Candidate Trump have shared a total of 30 million times on Facebook, while those supporting his opponent Hilary Clinton were shared eight million times. That form of messaging suggests the democratic process itself may be under new threat.

Statement of the problem

The spread of fake news on the internet, particularly the social media has caused much unrests and great concern for members of society, including the government, policymakers, organizations, institutions, businesses and citizens. Fake news is specifically designed to plant a seed of mistrust and exacerbate the existing social and cultural dynamics by misusing political, regional and religious undercurrents in our togetherness. Fake news is intentionally and verifiably false that is capable of misleading readers. In other words, fake news is an act of deliberately spreading untrue information, misinformation or disinformation about a person, organization, institution, political party, government, continent, etc and has an adverse impact on individuals and society as it deliberately persuades users to accept false beliefs that are shared to forward specific agendas.

The spread of fake news on social media becomes more concern as private university students especially the ones from average social status families who could easily afford and access smart phones, internet, computer, and power now sleeps on online. These sets of students believes and relay more on news and information gotten from social media about government policies, business

orientation, institutional information, personal and public information and tends to verify less of what is gotten on internet and easily shares them across friends, colleagues, parents, and other decision makers. Such information if happen to be fake or false, can potentially harm user's interest by negatively influence their decision. Thus, fake news and its viral circulation have become a grave concern in the era of social media, where anonymity, user-generated content and geographical distance may encourage fake-news sharing behaviour among private university students. It is on this note that the researchers tend to examine the influence of library use as correlate in curbing the spread of fake news on social media among private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. identify common types of fake news shared on social media by private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria.
2. determine how often and effectively private university students in Oyo State use library resources to evaluate news on social media.
3. examine the impact of library-offered digital literacy programme on students' ability to discern fake news from real information online.
4. investigate how students perceive the role of libraries in countering fake news on social media.

Literature Review

Fake news

Today university students face a challenge. They can access information on their mobile phone at a moment's notice than previous generations could access in a university library. However, much of the information digested by students today is questionable quality. This reality makes knowing how to properly search for, use and evaluate information a critical skill for the 21st century (Fosnacht, 2017). The ability to evaluate information is imperative for all individuals but is of particular importance to students studying to be media professionals, since these students will most likely be the journalists of the future and will fill the roles of gatekeepers and arbitrators of civic discourse. In this era of fake news, it can be harder

than ever for journalists to prove themselves objective and honest in their coverage of important news events where they can be met with not skepticism but outright rejection or denial. Journalist and other related information professions should be open to criticism on the stories they write and for news pieces to be dismissed as fake and lumped with the latest conspiracy theories shared on social media is a deeply troubling notion. Not all news pieces will be met with universal agreement but good reporting should inspire meaningful debate and tarring such pieces as fake news is undermining this notion (Farrell, 2017).

Many academic librarians agree that the current prominence of fake news in the public conversation has presented librarian with the opportunity and responsibility to assume a leadership role as trained information professionals in providing relevant information literacy instruction to students and to develop collaborative partnerships with the teaching faculty across the disciplines. Fake news is defined as the promotion and propagation of news articles in either printed or non-printed formats or both, these could include newspaper, television, social media, etc. The news stories distributed are designed to influence or manipulate users' opinions on a certain topic towards certain objectives. Fake News could also be referred to as Misinformation or Alternative Facts is most often used to describe completely fabricated stories, but can also be applied to a broader continuum of news (Gu and Yarochkin, 2017). Many news outlets will exhibit some form of explicit or implicit bias while not falling into the fake news category. Assessing the quality of the information source is crucial and it is up to every individual to evaluate the information and ensure that it is reliable and truthful.

Condensing a wide range of news gathering practices into a meaningful understanding and judgment has been a big problem for definitions of 'real news' in information profession for a long time now (Carlson, 2017). Along the same lines, overly general conceptualizations of the term 'fake news' can even be outright dangerous, as citizens struggle to distinguish legitimate news from fake news in a digital information environment (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017; UNESCO, 2018). Even more importantly, research has begun to show that 'fake' news is often understood as news one does not believe in,

thereby blurring the boundaries between facts and beliefs in a confusing digitalized world (Nielsen & Graves, 2017). Unhelpfully, scholars have been tempted to use the term to describe many different things, such as propagandistic messages (Khaldarova & Pantti, 2016) and fabricated news from short-lived websites (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). To make matters worse, political actors have seized the opportunity to use the term as a weapon to undermine any information that contradicts their own political agenda (Hanitzsch, Van Dalen, & Steindl, 2018; Nielsen & Graves, 2017).

Social Media as Vehicle of Fake News

Fake news on social media is of course not new, however, the extent to which it occurs today appears to be at alarming. Closely connected to the rise of the fake news debate are the challenges that the rise of the internet and social media presents for modern life. In an online news environment, information may be created and spread more cost-efficiently and quicker than ever before, and users are now able to participate in news production and dissemination processes. As such, classic selection mechanisms, such as trust in the gatekeeping function of information professional, are impaired (McNair, 2017; Nielsen & Graves, 2017) not only because it is increasingly challenging to differentiate between professional and unprofessional content (Stanford History Education Group, 2016) but also because information professionals themselves are now challenged in properly verifying digital information during the fake news production process. This challenge puts the assessment of information credibility increasingly with an overwhelmed user and studies show that even digital natives struggle with evaluating online information (Stanford History Education Group, 2016). In addition, digital advertising makes fake news financially attractive, as views or ‘clicks’ instead of the accuracy of the content create business success. This idea links fake news to the emergence of clickbait, that is, the creation of news content solely aimed at generating attention through sensational and emotionally appealing headlines.

These technological developments are met by a number of social and political trends. Most scholars connect the emergence of fake news to a larger crisis of trust in information professional. While most prominently discussed in the United

State, where a recent poll found that media trust has dropped to ‘a new low’ increasing mistrust towards news media is also a problem to such country (Swift, 2016).

Library use of private university students

Many studies have been carried out on library use. This is because it is the users that make the library relevant and its services come alive. A library that is not used is as good as dead as it cannot justify its existence. It is the use to which the library is put that infuses life into its resources and services. Hence, library use and user studies cannot outlive their usefulness. Reading books has a privileged status in today’s world, where knowledge and the ways it is disseminated accumulates and multiplies. Libraries are places where the habit of reading books can be acquired. Libraries increase student success at school and they help them to acquire the educational knowledge necessary for adapting to changing and evolving circumstances (Kachel 2007). There are many studies in the literature that indicate a positive relationship between students’ library use habits and their success at school and society (Lance, Rodney and Hamilton-Pennell, 2000). As the amount of research revealing the effect of libraries on student success at school increases, studies oriented towards the use of the library become more intensive. The studies regarding library use are usually focused on the extent to which students use the library their attitude towards the library, the respective characteristics of the individuals using and not using a library demographic characteristic affecting the use of the library and the effects of family, school and society on library use habits (Yilmaz, 2004).

Akande (2003) noted that the use of library resources is uppermost in the minds of the university libraries as this will enable the management know how best they can serve their users. Users’ study is thus regarded as a veritable tool for the assessment of libraries and their services. The study of Ozoemelem (2009) identified that informed library users know that university libraries have resources that are more comprehensive and scholarly than most web sites provide but the problem is that these resources they are not straightforward like that on the webs. Though users use university libraries for different purposes, Oyesiku and Oduwole (2004) study on the use of academic library showed that students use the library mostly during examinations period

and relays on social media for some other information needed. In a study of Igun and Adogbeji (2007) among the postgraduate students, majority of the students claimed that their main purpose of using the library is to update their knowledge and skills.

Among many users of the library are the private university students. This class of students is regarded as ‘socially influenced students’ because they have come from more advantageous homes. Comparative studies of private and public university studies have showed that the cost of studying in private university is far behind that of public university. The library use habit of students of these universities tends to be different from their counterparts in public universities. Therefore, how the private university students perceive the role of their university library matters a lot. The use of library resources and services is thus indispensable to the private university students in order to achieve their academic objectives. As a result, Olofinsawe and Oyeniyi (2010) affirmed that university libraries have to build strong collection of information resources in physical and digital format to cater for knowledge requirements of all their users. It is therefore necessary to take the needs of private university students into consideration in policy planning in any university library.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey design to examine library use as correlate in curbing the spread of fake news on social media among university students. This allowed the researchers to illicit information from the respondents via the use of questionnaire.

The Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria, comprising both undergraduate and postgraduate students of the institutions regardless of their demographic factors. The universities include: Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo; Atiba University, Oyo; Dominican University, Ibadan; First Technical University, Ibadan; Kola Daisi University, Ibadan and Lead City University, Ibadan.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample of three hundred and thirty-seven (337) students were randomly selected from six private universities in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Results

1. What are the most prevalent types of fake news shared on social media by private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table II: Prevalent fake news in private University

Prevalent fake news	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Mean	SD
Political fake news	77(22.8)	143(42.4)	110(32.6)	7(2.1)	2.8605	.78764
Health-related fake news	59(17.5)	142(42.1)	116(34.4)	20(5.9)	2.7122	.82209
Fake news related to celebrities and entertainment	102(30.3)	147(43.6)	74(22.0)	14(4.2)	3.0000	.83095
Fake news about local events in Oyo State	65(19.3)	134(39.8)	96(28.5)	42(12.5)	2.6588	.92864
Fake news related to international events	64(19.0)	132(39.2)	98(29.1)	43(12.8)	2.6439	.93106
Fake news about science and technology	59(17.5)	117(34.7)	113(33.5)	48(14.2)	2.5549	.94055
Education related fake news	51(18.1)	125(37.1)	115(34.1)	36(10.7)	2.6261	.90121
Fake news regarding religious topics	63(18.7)	135(70.1)	119(35.3)	20(5.9)	2.7151	.83569
Fake news about social issues and activism	76(22.6)	172(51.0)	78(23.1)	11(3.3)	2.9288	.76433
Economy and business fake news	71(21.1)	159(47.2)	74(22.0)	33(9.8)	2.7953	.88451

Table II reveals that private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria, perceive political fake news as prevalent, with 22.8% strongly agreeing and 42.4% agreeing (mean score 2.86), though opinions vary, as 32.6% disagree. Health-related fake news is also seen as prevalent, with 17.5% strongly agreeing and 42.1% agreeing (mean score 2.71), but there is notable disagreement (34.4%). Fake news about celebrities and entertainment is considered the most prevalent, with a mean score of 3.00, supported by 30.3% strongly agreeing and 43.6% agreeing, with lower disagreement (22.0%). Local events fake news is moderately prevalent (mean score 2.66), with more disagreement (28.5%). International events fake news is similarly perceived, with a mean score of 2.64 and significant variability in opinions. Science and technology fake news is seen as the least prevalent (mean score 2.55), with considerable disagreement (33.5%). Education-

related fake news also ranks low in prevalence (mean score 2.63), with mixed opinions. Religious-related fake news has a mean score of 2.72, with more consistency in responses. Social issues and activism fake news is relatively prevalent (mean score 2.93), with 22.6% strongly agreeing and 51.0% agreeing, and less variability in responses. Economy and business-related fake news is moderately prevalent (mean score 2.80), with moderate variability in opinions. Overall, fake news about celebrities, social issues, and politics is seen as most prevalent, while science, education, and international events are perceived as less common, with significant variability in student opinions.

2. To what extent do students find library resources effective in evaluating the accuracy of news on social media platforms?

Table III: Library Resources' Effectiveness against Fake News

Library Resources' Effectiveness	Very High Extent	High Extent	Low Extent	Very Low Extent	Mean	SD
Library resources help to verify accuracy of news on social media	63(18.7)	163(48.4)	76(22.6)	35(10.4)	2.7537	.87722
Library resources are valuable in evaluating news on social media	115(34.1)	177(52.5)	45(13.4)		3.2077	.65796
Library resources make it easy to determine if news on social media is fake or real	92(27.3)	184(54.6)	51(15.1)	10(3.0)	3.0623	.73536
I use library resources to fact-check information on social media	116(34.4)	151(44.8)	56(16.6)	14(4.2)	3.0950	.81825
Library resources enhance my ability to critically assess news shared on social media	106(31.5)	142(42.1)	71(21.1)	18(5.3)	2.9970	.86085
Resources for evaluating the accuracy of social media news can be found in the library	103(30.6)	130(38.6)	78(23.1)	26(7.7)	2.9199	.91748
I feel confident in the accuracy of news I find on social media when I use library resources	93(27.6)	164(48.7)	66(19.6)	14(4.2)	2.9970	.79992
I save time using library resources to verify information from social media	90(26.7)	180(53.4)	54(16.0)	13(3.9)	3.0297	.76318
Library resources improve my understanding of the information shared on social media	91(27.0)	178(52.8)	52(15.4)	16(4.7)	3.0208	.78463
I trust the information I verify through library resources than social media	93(27.6)	147(43.6)	86(25.5)	11(3.3)	2.9555	.81345

Table III evaluates the effectiveness of library resources in helping private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria, assess the accuracy of news on social media. The data shows that a significant portion of students (67.1%) believe these resources are effective, as indicated by a mean score of 2.75 and a standard deviation of 0.88. However, there is notable variability, with 33% of students expressing lower confidence in these resources. The most positively viewed aspect is the value of library resources for evaluating news, with a high mean score of 3.21 and a low standard deviation of 0.66, indicating consistent agreement among students. Additionally, 81.9% of students agree that these resources make it easier to determine the authenticity of news, reflected by a mean score of 3.06 and a standard deviation of 0.74. A majority of students (79.2%) actively use library resources for fact-checking, resulting in a mean score of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 0.82. However, a smaller portion (26.4%) is less convinced about the resources' effectiveness in enhancing critical thinking, as shown by a mean

score of 2.99 and a standard deviation of 0.86. While most students (69.2%) acknowledge the availability of necessary resources in libraries, the mean score of 2.92 and a higher standard deviation of 0.92 suggest varied experiences. Confidence in the accuracy of news verified through library resources is generally high (mean = 2.99, S.D = 0.80), though some students remain cautious. Additionally, 80.1% of students find library resources time-efficient for verifying information, with a mean score of 3.03 and a standard deviation of 0.76. Finally, students generally believe that library resources improve their understanding of social media content (mean = 3.02, S.D = 0.78), and there is relatively strong trust in library-verified information (mean = 2.96, S.D = 0.81), although some remain less certain.

3. What is the impact of library-offered digital literacy programme on private university students' ability to distinguish fake news from legitimate information online?

Table IV: Impact of Digital Literacy Programme

Impact of Digital Literacy Programme	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Mean	SD
Improved my ability to spot fake news	111(32.9)	159(47.2)	45(13.4)	22(6.5)	3.0653	.84966
Distinguish fake news from authentic one	113(33.5)	151(44.8)	52(15.4)	21(6.2)	3.0564	.85900
Digital literacy programme enhanced my critical thinking skills when assessing information online	100(29.7)	161(47.5)	64(19.0)	12(3.6)	3.0356	.79352
I evaluate the accuracy of news on social media using skills learned in library digital literacy programme	89(26.5)	171(50.7)	63(18.7)	14(4.2)	2.9941	.78677
Increased awareness of tactics used to spread fake news	95(28.2)	181(53.7)	44(13.1)	17(5.0)	3.0504	.78327
Digital literacy programme have made me more cautious when encountering news on social media	85(25.2)	188(55.8)	42(12.5)	22(6.5)	2.9970	.79992

I use knowledge from digital literacy programme to discern reliable sources from fake news	83(24.6)	177(52.5)	69(20.5)	8(2.4)	2.9941	.73999
Improved my online information evaluation skills	86(25.5)	186(55.2)	59(17.5)	6(1.8)	3.0445	.70781
Library's digital literacy programme gave me tools to verify the accuracy of news on social media	85(25.2)	59(47.2)	69(20.5)	24(7.1)	2.9050	.85732

Table IV assesses the impact of digital literacy programme offered by libraries on private university students' ability to distinguish fake news from legitimate information online, using four levels of agreement (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). A majority of students (32.9% strongly agree, 47.2% agree) report that these programme have improved their ability to spot fake news, with a mean score of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 0.85, indicating moderate variability. Similarly, 78.3% (33.5% strongly agree, 44.8% agree) believe the programme help them distinguish fake news from authentic news, with a mean score of 3.06 and a standard deviation of 0.86. Many students (29.7% strongly agree, 47.5% agree) also feel that their critical thinking skills have been enhanced, reflected in a mean score of 3.04 and a standard deviation of 0.79. Additionally, 77.2% (26.5% strongly agree, 50.7% agree) use these skills to evaluate news accuracy on social media, though some variability exists (mean = 2.99, S.D. = 0.79). Awareness of fake news tactics is high among students (28.2% strongly agree, 53.7% agree), with a mean score of 3.05 and a standard deviation of 0.78. Most students (25.2% strongly agree,

55.8% agree) report being more cautious online, reflected in a mean score of 2.99 and a standard deviation of 0.80. A significant number of students (24.6% strongly agree, 52.5% agree) apply knowledge to discern reliable sources, with a mean score of 2.99 and a standard deviation of 0.74. Moreover, 80.7% (25.5% strongly agree, 55.2% agree) feel their information evaluation skills have improved, with a mean score of 3.04 and a low standard deviation of 0.71. Finally, 72.4% (25.2% strongly agree, 47.2% agree) believe they have gained tools to verify news accuracy, though some skepticism remains (mean = 2.91, S.D. = 0.86). In summary, the data suggests that while digital literacy programme generally enhance students' ability to identify and evaluate fake news, some students report less confidence or inconsistent application of these skills, highlighting the need for ongoing support and potentially more tailored approaches.

4. How do private university students in Oyo State perceive the role of libraries in countering fake news on social media platforms?

Table V: Students' Perception of Library Role in curbing fake new

Students' Perception of Library Role	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Mean	SD
Libraries play a significant role in countering the spread of fake news on social media	83(24.6)	188(55.8)	48(14.2)	18(5.3)	2.9970	.77728

Library educate students about the dangers of fake news on social media	96(28.5)	176(52.2)	55(16.3)	10(3.0)	3.0623	.75137
Libraries are valuable resource in helping students discern fact from fiction online	100(29.7)	160(47.5)	60(17.8)	17(5.0)	3.0178	.82356
Students should actively seek guidance from libraries to combat fake news on social media	107(31.8)	169(50.1)	47(13.9)	14(4.2)	3.0950	.78483
Libraries have a responsibility to promote digital literacy and fake news awareness	118(35.0)	169(50.1)	44(13.1)	6(1.8)	3.1840	.72085
Libraries are crucial partners in addressing the issue of fake news on social media	112(33.2)	161(47.8)	53(15.7)	11(3.3)	3.1098	.78098
The role of libraries in combating fake news should be better acknowledged by students	80(23.7)	173(51.3)	71(21.2)	13(3.9)	2.9496	.77564
Libraries provide students with the knowledge needed to challenge fake news on social media	83(24.6)	166(49.3)	66(19.6)	22(6.5)	2.9199	.83601
Students should collaborate with libraries to reduce the impact of fake news on social media	97(28.5)	161(47.8)	61(18.1)	19(5.6)	2.9911	.83269

Table V indicates that students' perceptions of the role libraries play in combating fake news on social media. A significant majority of students agree that libraries are crucial in this effort, with 80.4% (24.6% strongly agree, 55.8% agree) recognizing their significant role, which reflected in a mean score of 2.9970 and a standard deviation of 0.77728. Furthermore, 80.7% of students (28.5% strongly agree, 52.2% agree) believe that libraries educate them about the dangers of fake news, as indicated by a mean score of 3.0623 and a standard deviation of 0.75137. Libraries were seen as valuable resources for discerning fact from

fiction by 77.2% of students (29.7% strongly agree, 47.5% agree), with a mean score of 3.0178 and a standard deviation of 0.82356. Additionally, 81.9% (31.8% strongly agree, 50.1% agree) believe students should actively seek guidance from libraries to combat fake news, reflected in a mean score of 3.0950 and a standard deviation of 0.78483. There was a strong agreement (83.1% with a mean score of 3.1840 and S.D. = 0.72085) that libraries have a responsibility to promote digital literacy and fake news awareness, and 81.0% (33.2% strongly agree, 47.8% agree) see libraries as crucial partners in addressing fake

news, with a mean score of 3.1098 and a standard deviation of 0.78098. Also, 75.0% of students (23.7% strongly agree, 51.3% agree) believe the role of libraries in combating fake news should be better acknowledged, with a mean score of 2.9496 and a standard deviation of 0.77564. Finally, 73.9% of students (24.6% strongly agree, 49.3% agree) agree that libraries provide the necessary knowledge to challenge fake news, and 76.3% (28.5% strongly agree, 47.8% agree) believe students should collaborate with libraries to reduce the impact of fake news. The mean scores for these are 2.9199 (S.D. = 0.83601) and 2.9911 (S.D. = 0.83269), respectively. Therefore, the data indicates that students generally perceive libraries as essential allies in the fight against fake news, though some believe this role could be more widely acknowledged and utilized.

Discussion of the findings

Most prevalent types of fake news shared on social media by private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria

The findings of this study revealed that the most prevalent fake news shared among private university students on social media include news related to celebrities and entertainment, news about social issues and activism, political news, economy and business news and news regarding religious topics while news regarding science and technology as well as education related news has less attention. This finding has proven why most young adolescent youths in tertiary institution have been used for political thuggery and others live in coping and imitating some celebrities instead of fulfilling their own dreams. The findings also showed why many students, especially those in private universities have less attention to their study believing that their money (or their parent's) can afford them the grade they desire. This finding is in consonant with the findings of Baym (2005), who identified that fake news was originally applied to political satire and gain. This finding also agreed with the findings of Wardle (2017) who sees fake news as fabricated news that is produced either for profit (business) or for political purposes.

Extent to which students find library resources effective in evaluating the accuracy of news on social media platforms

From the findings of this study, it was showed that the respondents greatly find library resources to be valuable in evaluating news on social media, other percentage admitted that they use library resources to fact-check information on social media. Another section of the respondents agreed that library resources make it easier to determine if news on social media is fake or real. This finding is an indication that students of private universities are found of using the university libraries, also, the findings is an indication that the libraries in private universities are well equipped with suffocated resources that are capable of revealing fake news from real news. Some of this information resources may include indexes, journals, serial materials and reference materials. This finding aligned with the findings of Ozoemelem (2009) who identified that informed library users know that university libraries have resources that are more comprehensive and scholarly than most web sites provide, such that if well utilized, will enable users to distinct the reality of materials on the webs. However, the present findings is in contrast with the findings of Oyesiku and Oduwale (2004) who carried out a use of academic library and the result showed that students use the library mostly during examinations period and relays on social media for some other information needed.

Impact of library-offered digital literacy programme on private university students' ability to distinguish fake news from legitimate information online

The findings on digital literacy programme among private university students identified that digital literacy programme has helped them to improved their ability to spot fake news, distinguish fake news from authentic one, increase their awareness of tactics used to spread fake news, improved their online information evaluation skills and enhanced their critical thinking skills when assessing information online. This finding has unveiled the efficacy of digital literacy programme among private university students. This finding aligned with the findings of Allcott and Gentzkow (2017) who identified that overly general conceptualizations of fake news can even be outright dangerous, as citizens struggle to distinguish legitimate news from fake news in a

digital information environment, only digital literacy programme can help.

Perception of private university students on the role of libraries in countering fake news on social media platforms

The findings of this study showed that students of private universities in Oyo state, Nigeria perceived that university libraries have the responsibility to promote digital literacy and fake news awareness among its users, they also feel that libraries are crucial partners in addressing the issue of fake news on social media. It was revealed that students of private universities perceived that students should actively seek the guidance from their libraries to combat fake news on social media. This findings has obviously showed that university libraries have the key role to play in curbing the spread of fake news on social media among its students. Peradventure the university libraries fail in this role, the society will be at the risk of feeding on fake news. This is because this students can afford smart phones and computers and have the capacity to sleep on internet 24/7. This findings is in consonant with the findings of Kachel (2007), who identified that libraries are places where the habit of reading books and other information resources can be acquired and increases student success at school and help them to acquire the educational knowledge necessary for adapting to changing and evolving circumstances in the society.

Conclusion

The study sheds light on the significant issue of fake news among private university students in Oyo State, Nigeria, highlighting the types of misinformation that are most prevalent and the resources students use to combat this challenge. The findings reveal that fake news related to celebrities, social issues, and politics are particularly widespread, reflecting the interests and concerns of the student population. The study also underscores the importance of library resources in verifying the accuracy of news, as well as the positive impact of digital literacy programme in enhancing students' ability to distinguish between real and fake news. To address these issues, the study recommendations were made.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Private university libraries should expand their role as a hub for fact-checking by offering workshops and providing access to tools that help students verify the authenticity of information. Libraries should further promote these resources and encourage students to use them frequently.
2. Awareness campaigns should be conducted to inform students about the potential impact of fake news on their perceptions and decision-making processes. These campaigns should focus on educating students about the tactics used in spreading fake news and the importance of relying on credible sources.
3. Private universities should regularly evaluate and update their digital literacy programme to ensure they are effective in equipping students with the skills needed to distinguish between real and fake news.
4. Students should be encouraged to collaborate more closely with libraries to combat the spread of fake news. Initiatives such as student-led workshops or peer-review groups can help reinforce the role of libraries in this effort.
5. Students should explore the use of technology, such as AI-powered fact-checking tools, to help quickly and accurately assess the validity of news shared on social media.

By implementing these recommendations, private university libraries can play a significant role in mitigating the spread of fake news and enhancing students' ability to critically evaluate the information they encounter online.

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